

Original Research

A Framework of Critical Success Factors Affecting the Business to Business Sales Performance

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Abstract

The role and nature of business-to-business (B2B) sales performance has evolved since the end of the 20th century, largely due to technological, organizational, and societal changes. Nevertheless, literature has not yet been able to evolve along with it. The literature lacks research that exclusively shows a framework for determining the critical factors affecting the success of sales performance at the business-to-business (B2B) level. Therefore, this research has been conducted using a mixed method (qualitative and quantitative) to determine the impact of critical factors on the success of business-to-business (B2B) sales performance. At first, the qualitative method of systematic review was used. According to this method, out of 269 articles related to the topic, the results of 40 articles published in reliable databases from 1980 to 2022 have been reviewed and analyzed. Further, interviews were conducted with industry experts in this field, and data analysis was done with the help of SPSS software. The results of the research indicate that success in B2B sales performance may be influenced by 31 effective factors related to four dimensions: individual, organizational, environmental, and customer level. Finally, the limitations of the research and recommendations regarding success in B2B sales performance are provided.

Keywords: Critical Success Factors, Mixed Method, Sales Performance, Systematic Review, Qualitative Method, Quantitative Method.

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Introduction

Today, according to the existing environmental situation, which includes increasing competitive pressure, technological changes, and destructive market changes, it is necessary for companies and organizations to adapt to the changed environment as soon as possible (Marquardt et al., 2018). This situation has caused businesses to sell products and services in a market that has become more competitive; Therefore, one of the main concerns of organizations is increasing the success of sales performance (Hartmann et al., 2018). Sales performance is the goal of any business through either top-level revenue or bottom-line profit. As a result, sales performance has been widely recognized as a critical area of research and is vital to nearly every business's success (Javalgi et al., 2014; Mai & Liao, 2022; Edwards et al., 2023). The growing interest in sales performance is largely due to the significant role played by direct selling in the B2B marketing domain (Itani et al., 2022). For this reason, companies try to maintain, stabilize and/or improve their position in the competitive market by increasing sales performance (Joanbakht et al., 2021). One of the ways to increase sales performance is to pay attention to critical success factors that play a vital role in driving sales performance by focusing efforts, aligning strategies, offering direction, promoting continuous improvement, and encouraging accountability and transparency (Enos et al., 2007). The potential application and usefulness of the CSFs concept generated considerable interest in industry, as CSFs seemed to be an aid to management to strategise, plan, manage, monitor and achieve organisational goals (Ram & Corkindale, 2014). Given the apparent relevance for industry, researchers saw the need to identify CSFs to help solve practice-oriented problems, which resulted in the growth of scholarly publications on CSFs over the past four decades (Karuppusami and Gandhinathan, 2006; Khan et al., 2009; Ram & Corkindale, 2014).

Therefore, understanding the critical factors that determine success in sales performance has been a prominent issue in marketing and industrial sales research (Verbeke et al., 2011). Critical success factors (CSFs) are complex and have not been sufficiently studied. No critical success factor is common to all companies and industries, and critical success factors vary from industry to industry, from market to market. This success is sometimes a subjective perception of decision makers or a perception of the value provided, which is evaluated by the customer or end user of a service and is very difficult to generalize. Consequently, efforts to analyze and define critical success factors must consider the specific characteristics of each specific domain. A number of critical success factors emerge as a result of considering all industry/market/company specific factors and characteristics (Selimovic et al., 2020).

Following this issue, some researchers such as Churchill et al. (1985) and Verberke et al. (2011) determined the effective factors for the success of sales performance, but the literature lacks contemporary studies that exclusively determine the critical factors that influence the success of business-to-business sales performance. These factors include internal factors of the organization, at the customer level, and the external environment. As stated, the previous research did not consider a comprehensive review of the mentioned factors that guarantee success in sales performance, and today, based on that, requests are needed to review these factors (Sullivan et al., 2012; Pullins et al., 2017).

According to the comments of some researchers such as Aydin et al. (2017) and Limbu et al. (2016), the factors proposed by Churchill et al. (1985) and Walker et al. (1977) cannot be considered the most prominent predictors of sales performance. The next shortcoming of previous research is that most of the performance studies were at the business-to-consumer (B2C) level (Rodriguez et al., 2022). Obviously, a consumer's experience in a B2B market environment is different from his experience in a B2C environment. B2B customers are industrial customers, and organizations try to influence customer expectations and perceptions (Habel et al., 2016) to increase their productivity and remain in the competitive environment (Singh & Abraham, 2010). In addition, the researchers noted that the findings about the success factors of sales performance are not necessarily for business-to-business sales. Business-to-business sales are very complex, often lengthy, and include their own decision-making processes (Verberke et al., 2011). According to these issues, many vital factors in business-to-business sales are not under the control of the company and the seller and may require them to allocate more time and organizational resources. Improving the success of B2B sales performance is an important issue for researchers and experts in this field (Frino & Desiderio, 2013), and for the survival and success of companies and their management, defining the critical success factors in sales performance is very important. Researchers agree that focusing on some truly critical factors is necessary so that resources and capacities are not wasted (Selimovic et al., 2020). Therefore, in the current research, we are looking to investigate the vital factors affecting the success of sales performance. As a result, the general question of the current research:

What are the most important critical factors affecting the success of Business to Business (B2B) sales performance? And how is the determining framework of the identified factors?

Literature review

Critical success factors

The concept of critical success factors was first defined in the second half of the 20th century, in papers by D. R. Daniel (1961), John F. Rockart and Christine V. Bullen (1979; 1981). Rockart and Bullen (1981, p. 7) were the first to define the critical success factors as “*the limited number of areas in which satisfactory results will ensure successful competitive performance for the individual, department or organization*” (Selimovic et al., 2020). These are “the few key areas where things must go right” for the business to flourish and for the manager's goals to be attained (Ram & Corkindale, 2014). In other words, the critical success factors are characteristics, situations or variables that, if properly maintained, supported, and managed, play an undeniable role in the company's success. In any field of activity, there are countless factors that fundamentally affect the expected results; Therefore, strategy can be successful if these factors are controlled and used skillfully (Manian & Arabsarakhi, 2008). These factors are essential for business prosperity, and that is why organizations should focus on them to be successful in various fields such as sales performance (Selimovic et al., 2020).

Sales performance

Performance is defined as the evaluation of an employee's behavior and activities in line with organizational goals (Azizi & Khorasani, 2014). But there are several definitions of "sales performance". Rodriguez et al. (2012) provided two definitions of sales performance. According to them, sales performance focuses on behaviors that strengthen the relationship between buyers and sellers. Additionally, sales performance is an important aspect of salesperson performance measurement and is reflected in achieving quota, average bill size growth, increased sales productivity, and increased overall revenue. Therefore, sales performance is focused on the two criteria of relationship and result. Chawla et al. (2020) also define sales performance as effectiveness, which refers to the evaluation of objective results such as sales volume, market share, percentage of quota obtained, and the number of new customers added. In their research, Azizi and Khorasani (2013) pointed out that sales performance is the evaluation of the sales force in helping the organization achieve organizational goals. Ideally, the sales function is an integral part of an organization's strategy. Sales performance measures should be consistent with organizational mission and goals and encourage salesperson behaviors that support desired outcomes. While functions such as manufacturing, accounting, research and development, supply chain, etc., generally add to company costs, marketing and sales activities generate revenue. Sales performance can be defined as the quantitative contribution of sales representatives towards business goals (Aydin et al., 2017).

Research background

According to previous research, Churchill et al. (1985) were among the first researchers who addressed the determining factors affecting sales performance. In their research, they studied the articles that covered the period from 1918 to 1985. The factors affecting sales performance were divided into six categories, including: role perception, talent, skill level, motivation, personal, organizational, and environmental factors. Churchill et al. (1985) dealt with the issues in detail, and we try to cover more and newer issues in this research. According to Jaworski's research (1988), the environmental influencing factors of a marketing unit are divided into three categories: the macro environment (political, social, legal, economic, and technological), the operational environment (stakeholders such as customers or suppliers with whom the company directly deals) and the organizational environment. While the macro and operational environments consist of variables in the external environment (e.g., economic uncertainty), the organizational environment deals with aspects within the firm (e.g., training). Therefore, in this research, we will use Jaworski's framework (1988) to divide the discussion of general influencing factors, and we will consider the operational environment and the remote environment as the external environment and the internal environment of the organization as the organizational environment. In 2011 Verbrk et al. revise the classification scheme for sales performance determinants devised by Walker et al. (1977) and estimate both the predictive validity of its sub-categories and the impact of a range of moderators on determinant-sales performance relationships. The basic drivers of this research are the six categories of predictors to explain the marginal variance in sales performance (in order of predictive validity), which include: role perception, skill levels, talent, motivation, personal characteristics and drivers of organizational

environmental variables. These stimuli were used from Churchill et al.'s (1985) research, which was previously developed by Walker et al. (1977). However, in their 2011 research, Verberk et al. showed subgroups that influence sales performance: sales knowledge, adaptability, role ambiguity, talent, and work engagement. Chavala et al. 2020 developed the research of Verberk et al. 2011. They found three factors that affect sales performance, including technological factors, socio-psychological factors related to the job, and strategic factors. However Igwe et al. (2020) only stated technology as an important and effective factor in the progress and success of sales performance in businesses. They stated that technology improves the external and internal communication of businesses, and based on that, they identified factors that significantly and positively affect sales performance. In other words, using technology, today's salesperson is under pressure to do more in less time, which is why technological advancements have become an integral part of the sales process. Many organizations spend significant human and financial resources to equip their sales force with technology (Rodriguez & Roman, 2016). Hall et al. (2022); and Herjanto and Franklin (2019) noted the use of artificial intelligence to enhance the performance of B2B sales. Some researchers found the effect of social media on sales performance to be very effective (e.g., Itani et al., 2022; Treho et al., 2022; Bowen et al., 2021; Chawla et al., 2020; Guenzi & Nijssen, 2020; and Ancillai et al., 2019). Thaichon et al. (2018) emphasized in their research that the use of Internet technology will affect the organization's sales structure and, as a result, improve sales performance. However, Bolander et al. (2014) listed the training given to sales forces as a critical factor in improving sales performance. Hogevoid et al. (2021) examined a framework of sales performance drivers at the business-to-business level, which includes : (1) interpersonal abilities, including communication skills, as well as (2) the degree of adaptability, considering the salesperson's ability to modify sales approach and behavior. (3) knowledge related to sales, including market and product knowledge skills; and (4) the use of technology by sellers. They checked that the training given to the salespeople to increase their skills is effective in improving the performance of the method. Among them is training in the field of weakening implicit bias by using transformative conversation. In other words, to improve sales performance, salespeople must be able to moderate and control implicit biases that are effective in sales relationships (Stephens & Baskerville, 2022). Dugan et al. (2020) in addition to training, reward, technology, and ethical issues, were also listed as important in the success of sales performance. Among the past research, Van Tien et al. (2019) discussed training in the field of effective coaching in sales as a factor affecting sales performance. To better understand the importance of training, Ogilvy et al. (2018) stated that the use of common technology tools of the seller-customer, which is social media, will not work well without training the employees. The results of the research of Matthews and his colleagues in 2016 show that customer orientation, training, and support of the supervisor have an effect on sales performance. However Keillor et al. (2000) only mention the dimension of customer orientation. Jaramillo et al. (2006) examined the ethical climate, intuition, comparison of organizational identity, and organizational trust of positive organizational support in their research. Gulati et al. (2004) studies showed that internal locus of control, learning orientation, and sales-related Internet training are positively related to a salesperson's Internet use, and salesperson's age has a negative relationship with Internet use.

Furthermore, the results have supported a positive relationship between a sales representative's Internet use and sales performance. Valtakoski's (2015) research showed that salespeople can influence buyer behavior to improve company sales performance by directly reducing the intangibility of the sales proposition or indirectly increasing buyer trust in the seller. Also, social media will improve sales performance by increasing customer satisfaction (cited in Agnihotri et al., 2016). Of course, researchers showed that even in the absence of social media, customer satisfaction with a salesperson has a positive correlation with the salesperson's objective sales performance (Blessing & Netter, 2019). Since customer satisfaction directly leads to repurchase behavior, the level of customer satisfaction will positively affect both sales performance and firm growth (Ko et al., 2022; Simon et al., 2009). Stuart Mill considered the reward structure to be effective on sales performance (Stewart, 1996). Kaynak et al. (2016) concluded that organizational customer orientation has a significant effect on sales performance, customer satisfaction, and salespeople's comparative sales behavior. Increased organizational identification tension can negatively affect customer satisfaction and sales performance.

Therefore, it is necessary to use the leadership styles of sales managers (charisma vs. transaction), and together with the appropriate control system (behavioral control vs. result), organizational tension can be avoided (Kraus et al., 2015). Wang and Miao (2015) found focus to be an important factor in organizational sales performance. Yang et al. (2011) investigated effective personal characteristics such as conscientiousness, extroversion, and self-efficacy. Baldauf and Cravens (2002) listed individual abilities, industry growth, sales planning, sales timing, and product type as effective in better sales performance. Sohi et al. (1996) consider the understanding of market competition as a factor in sales performance success. Anaza et al. (2018) showed that role empathy positively moderates favorable selling behaviors (listening and adaptive selling behaviors) that subsequently increase in-role (expected) and extra-role (discretionary) performance. Mariadoss et al., (2014) consider the influence of different individual skills on sales performance, such as consulting ability, experience and expertise. Leigh et al., (2014) focuses on salesperson knowledge, targeting skills, and technical knowledge that influence sales performance.

Table 1. Key factors extracted from the previous research

No.	Critical Factors	Scholars/Year
1	Technology-Artificial intelligence	Hall et al., 2022/ Herjanto & Franklin, 2019
2	Technology- social media	Itani et al., 2022/ Terho et al., 2022/ Bowen et al., 2022/ Ancillai et al., 2019
3	Education	Stephens & Baskerville, 2020/ Igwe et al., 2020/ Bolander et al., 2014
4	Satisfaction	Ko et al., 2022/Blessing & Natter, 2019/ Simon et al., 2009
5	Technology -Education- Interpersonal ability- Degree of compatibility- Sales knowledge	Hogevold et al., 2021

No.	Critical Factors	Scholars/Year
6	Technology- Education	Guenzi & Nijssen, 2020/ Ogilvie et al., 2018
7	Technology -Education- reward- Moral issues	Dugan et al., 2020
8	Technology- Internet	Thaichon et al., 2018
9	Education- Customer Orientation Organizational support	Matthews et al., 2016
10	Sympathy- listen	Anaza et al., 2018
11	Technology	Rodriguez & Roman, 2016
12	social media- Satisfaction	Agnihotri et al., 2016
13	Customer Orientation	Kaynak et al., 2016
14	Customer Trust	Valtakoski, 2015
15	Lack of organizational tension- method of leadership- Control system- thinking style	Kraus et al., 2015
16	Experience-Expertise-Intuition-Target	Mariadoss et al., 2014
17	Sales knowledge- Expertise- Target	Leigh et al., 2014
18	Motivation- Conscientiousness- extroversion- Efficacy	Yang et al., 2011
19	Degree of compatibility- Sales knowledge- Expertise- motivation- Perception in role- Talent- Job conflict	Verberke et al., 2011
20	Moral issues- Organizational support- Organizational Trust	Jaramillo et al., 2006
21	Focus	Wang & Miao, 2015
22	Technology -Education- Internet	Gulati et al., 2004
23	Individual ability- Industry growth- planning- Timing- product type	Baldauf & Cravens, 2002
24	Customer Orientation	Keillor et al., 2000
25	reward	Stewart, 1996
26	Competition	Sohi, 1996

Methodology

The present research was conducted using a mixed method; which respectively include the qualitative and quantitative methods respective. In the first part, a systematic review method was used to identify the dimensions and factors affecting the investigated phenomenon, i.e., sales performance. In the second part, which includes the quantitative phase of the research, a survey method has been used to obtain the views of the researched statistical community. The systematic review refers to identifying, evaluating, and interpreting all the research related to the research topic to summarize the articles about the comprehensive and new understanding of the phenomena (Kitchenham et al., 2004). The steps of systematic literature review are: 1. Identification of research questions 2. Identification of inclusion and exclusion criteria, 3. Search using relevant keywords, 4. Extraction and combination of data. Therefore, the research questions of this article are: 1) What are the most important critical factors affecting the success of sales performance at the? 2) What is the determining framework of the identified factors?

Inclusion/exclusion criteria in this research are: only documents printed in English are included, and documents printed in high-quality Web of Science and Scopus databases are included. Because these databases are complementary, they cover each other's strengths and weaknesses and increase the validity of the research. The related journals were of high impact factor, so the quality assurance is reasonable. It will be included until 2022. For this reason, we used 1980; Because the sales environment has changed dramatically since the 1980s (Thaichon et al., 2018; Harmon & Funk, 2014; Marshall et al., 1999).

Key words used in the research included: "critical success factors" OR "organizational factors" OR "internal factors" OR "external factors" AND "sales performance" OR "Success in sales" OR "Salesperson Performance" OR "Sales Effectiveness" which have been searched in Web of Science and Scopus databases. The results of this search led to the identification of 269 documents. Quantitative and qualitative research works are also kept; Because researchers usually use both methods in this research field. Also, the article should be conducted at the B2B level if possible, and the article should report at least one important determinant of sales performance. Finally, 40 articles out of 269 reviewed articles are eligible for further analysis. Also, A was used in the survey method self-administrative questionnaire was completed by experts in this field at the University of Mazandaran and companies based in Sari Science and Technology Park.

Analysis and findings

In the first part of the data analysis, the obtained factors have been designed as a questionnaire according to previous research. Content validity was used to determine the validity of the questionnaire. The content validity of a test is usually determined by experts in the subject under study. The mentioned questionnaire was checked by a group of professors, and after receiving the opinions of the professors, some of the suggested factors were changed and replaced. Finally, the questionnaire was revisited, and the validity of the content of the questionnaire was checked and confirmed by the professors, and their suggestions were used to correct the defects of the questions in the questionnaire. After ensuring the validity of the questions, the data collection process began. Cronbach's alpha is used to measure reliability through the final data. Cronbach's alpha calculated by SPSS software is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of processing

	Frequency	Percentage
Valid cases	30	98.8
Unanswered	1	3.2
Total	31	100

According to Table 2, all the experts answered the questions completely. The second output is shown in Table 3. This table examines the reliability of the test. Since the value of Cronbach's alpha (0.816) is greater than 0.7, the test has acceptable reliability.

Table 3. Reliability

Number of Items	Cronbach's alpha
42	0.863

Table 4. The results of data analysis to determine Reliability

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Role	165.4333	169.771	.285	.861
Consultation	165.5333	166.671	.311	.861
Thinking	165.4667	169.430	.256	.862
Intuition	165.7000	159.321	.539	.855
Experience	165.0667	169.513	.293	.861
Proficiency	165.1667	171.109	.183	.863
Sympathy	166.0667	162.892	.457	.858
Talent	166.0667	162.547	.526	.856
Individual ability	165.5667	169.702	.188	.863
Motivation	165.4333	163.909	.533	.857
Technology	165.5000	168.466	.296	.861
Economic factors	165.6333	167.826	.280	.861
Industry growth	166.0667	162.961	.367	.860
Social factors	165.5333	167.223	.181	.866
Product type	165.2000	167.338	.398	.859
Planning for sales	165.7333	162.202	.523	.856
Time	165.2000	174.924	-.072	.866
Knowledge	165.7333	162.616	.567	.856
Degree of compatibility	165.5667	166.806	.357	.860
Responsibility	166.0000	160.621	.540	.856
Self-efficacy	165.6333	171.895	.073	.866
Extrovert	165.7000	168.838	.296	.861
Work engagement	165.7667	159.771	.456	.857
Social media	166.0667	160.961	.443	.858
Ai	165.5667	164.392	.405	.859
Internet	165.4000	169.214	.255	.862
Training	165.2667	167.237	.412	.859
Customer orientation	165.5333	165.844	.300	.861
Moral Issues	165.8667	167.016	.289	.861
Reward	165.5000	159.914	.565	.855
Organizational support	165.1000	168.300	.282	.861
Customer trust	165.9000	163.266	.590	.856
Lack of organizational tension	165.2333	168.806	.209	.863
Satisfaction	165.7000	165.045	.397	.859

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Method of leadership	165.8333	171.040	.101	.865
Control system	165.5000	167.707	.314	.861
Targeting	165.5333	164.395	.473	.858
Competitive	165.4000	165.076	.541	.857
Organizational trust	166.0667	166.823	.338	.860
Organizational focus	165.6333	168.378	.237	.862
Interpersonal abilities	165.5000	171.776	.088	.865
Effective listening	165.6000	172.731	.066	.865

In Table 4, in the second column, the mean is the average of the total number of questions in case the desired question is removed, the third column is the variance of the questions in case the desired question is removed, the fourth column is the degree of correlation of the question with all the questions in the questionnaire and the last column Cronbach's alpha in It shows the removal of the desired question. For example, if the question related to effective listening is removed, Cronbach's alpha coefficient changes to 0.864.

In the following, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used to ensure the normality of the data. If the significance level is less than 0.05 at the error level 0.05, the opposite assumption or the same claim will be confirmed. The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for the four main factors and subjects of the research can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

		Role	Consultation	Thinking	Intuition	Experience	Proficiency	Sympathy	Talent	Individual ability	Motivation	Technology	Economic factors	Industry growth	Social factors	Product type	
N		30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	28	30	
Normal Parameters	Mean	4.2	4.1	4.167	3.933	4.567	4.4667	3.5667	3.5667	4.0667	4.2	4.1333	4	3.5667	4.0357	4.4333	
	Std. Deviation	0.551	0.845	0.648	1.015	0.568	0.5714	0.8976	0.8172	0.7849	0.7144	0.6815	0.7878	1.0727	1.2013	0.6261	
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.375	0.286	0.302	0.22	0.377	0.325	0.319	0.335	0.266	0.244	0.278	0.2	0.199	0.253	0.317	
	Positive	0.375	0.214	0.302	0.154	0.241	0.293	0.215	0.231	0.234	0.244	0.278	0.2	0.168	0.211	0.256	
	Negative	-0.29	-0.29	-0.265	-0.22	-0.377	-0.325	-0.319	-0.335	-0.266	-0.235	-0.256	-0.2	-0.199	-0.253	-0.317	
Test Statistic		0.375	0.286	0.302	0.22	0.377	0.325	0.319	0.335	0.266	0.244	0.278	0.2	0.199	0.253	0.317	
Asymp. Sig. (2-Tailed) ^C		0	0	0	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.004	0.004	0	0	
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-Tailed) ^D	Sig.		0	0	0	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.004	0.004	0	0	
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.003	0.003	0	0
		Upper Bound	0	0	0	0.002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.006	0.006	0	0

Table 5. One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (Continued)

		Organizational support	Customer trust	Lack of organizational tension	Satisfaction	Method of leadership	Control system	Targeting	competitive	Organizational Trust	Organizational focus	Interpersonal abilities	Effective listening
N		30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	4.5333	3.7333	4.4	3.9333	3.8	4.1333	4.1	4.233	3.5667	4	4.133	4.033
	Std. Deviation	0.7303	0.69149	0.855	0.8277	0.887	0.7303	0.7589	0.626	0.77385	0.8305	0.776	0.615
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.372	0.317	0.325	0.232	0.323	0.294	0.281	0.312	0.246	0.3	0.235	0.322
	Positive	0.261	0.25	0.241	0.201	0.244	0.272	0.252	0.312	0.235	0.233	0.202	0.322
	Negative	-0.372	-0.317	-0.325	-0.232	-0.32	-0.294	-0.281	-0.26	-0.246	-0.3	-0.235	-0.31
Test Statistic		0.372	0.317	0.325	0.232	0.323	0.294	0.281	0.312	0.246	0.3	0.235	0.322
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) ^c		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed) ^d	Sig.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Upper Bound	0	0	0	0.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.001

As can be seen, the significance level for the questions is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (normality) is rejected, and the opposite hypothesis (non-normality) is accepted. Therefore, in line with the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, non-parametric tests should be used to test the identified factors. Regarding the answer to the main question of the research, we will examine the data obtained from the questionnaire for the identified factors by means of a binomial test to determine which of them have been approved by the experts and which have been rejected. In the implementation of this test, we defined three cut-off points. Also, we considered the confidence level of the test to be 95%. So, if the significance level is less than 0.05, the opposite assumption is accepted. In Table 6, you can see the results of the binomial test to answer the main question of the research.

Table 6. The results of binomial test

Binomial Test															
		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)			Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)
Role	Group 1	≤ 3	2	0.07	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Industrygrowth	Group 1	≤ 3	14	0.47	0.50	0.856	.856 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	28	0.93					Group 2	> 3	16	0.53			
	Total		30	1.00					Total		30	1.00			
Consultation	Group 1	≤ 3	5	0.17	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Socialfactors	Group 1	≤ 3	7	0.25	0.50	0.013	.013 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	25	0.83					Group 2	> 3	21	0.75			
	Total		30	1.00					Total		28	1.00			
Thinking	Group 1	≤ 3	4	0.13	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Producttype	Group 1	≤ 3	2	0.07	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	26	0.87					Group 2	> 3	28	0.93			
	Total		30	1.00					Total		30	1.00			
Intuition	Group 1	≤ 3	10	0.33	0.50	0.099	.099 ^a	Planningforsales	Group 1	≤ 3	8	0.27	0.50	0.016	.016 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	20	0.67					Group 2	> 3	22	0.73			
	Total		30	1.00					Total		30	1.00			
Experience	Group 1	≤ 3	1	0.03	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Time	Group 1	≤ 3	1	0.03	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	29	0.97					Group 2	> 3	29	0.97			
	Total		30	1.00					Total		30	1.00			

Binomial Test															
		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)			Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)
Proficiency	Group 1	<= 3	1	0.03	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Knowledge	Group 1	<= 3	8	0.27	0.50	0.016	.016 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	29	0.97			Group 2		> 3	22	0.73				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Sympathy	Group 1	<= 3	11	0.37	0.50	0.200	.200 ^a	Degree of compatibility	Group 1	<= 3	7	0.23	0.50	0.005	.005 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	19	0.63			Group 2		> 3	23	0.77				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Talent	Group 1	<= 3	11	0.37	0.50	0.200	.200 ^a	Responsibility	Group 1	<= 3	13	0.43	0.50	0.585	.585 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	19	0.63			Group 2		> 3	17	0.57				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Individual ability	Group 1	<= 3	6	0.20	0.50	0.001	.001 ^a	Self-efficacy	Group 1	<= 3	8	0.27	0.50	0.016	.016 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	24	0.80			Group 2		> 3	22	0.73				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Motivation	Group 1	<= 3	5	0.17	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Extrovert	Group 1	<= 3	7	0.23	0.50	0.005	.005 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	25	0.83			Group 2		> 3	23	0.77				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Technology	Group 1	<= 3	5	0.17	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Work engagement	Group 1	<= 3	9	0.30	0.50	0.043	.043 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	25	0.83			Group 2		> 3	21	0.70				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Economic factors	Group 1	<= 3	9	0.30	0.50	0.043	.043 ^a	Social media	Group 1	<= 3	12	0.40	0.50	0.362	.362 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	21	0.70			Group 2		> 3	18	0.60				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Ai	Group 1	<= 3	6	0.20	0.50	0.001	.001 ^a	Satisfaction	Group 1	<= 3	9	0.30	0.50	0.043	.043 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	24	0.80			Group 2		> 3	21	0.70				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				

Binomial Test															
		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)			Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)	Exact Sig. (2-Tailed)
Internet	Group 1	<= 3	4	0.13	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Method of leadership	Group 1	<= 3	8	0.27	0.50	0.016	.016 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	26	0.87			Group 2		> 3	22	0.73				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Training	Group 1	<= 3	2	0.07	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Control system	Group 1	<= 3	4	0.13	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	28	0.93			Group 2		> 3	26	0.87				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Customer orientation	Group 1	<= 3	5	0.17	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Targeting	Group 1	<= 3	5	0.17	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	25	0.83			Group 2		> 3	25	0.83				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Moral issues	Group 1	<= 3	9	0.30	0.50	0.043	.043 ^a	Competitive	Group 1	<= 3	3	0.10	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	21	0.70			Group 2		> 3	27	0.90				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Reward	Group 1	<= 3	4	0.13	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Organizational trust	Group 1	<= 3	14	0.47	0.50	0.856	.856 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	26	0.87			Group 2		> 3	16	0.53				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Organizational support	Group 1	<= 3	2	0.07	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Organizational focus	Group 1	<= 3	6	0.20	0.50	0.001	.001 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	28	0.93			Group 2		> 3	24	0.80				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Customer trust	Group 1	<= 3	10	0.33	0.50	0.099	.099 ^a	Interpersonal abilities	Group 1	<= 3	7	0.23	0.50	0.005	.005 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	20	0.67			Group 2		> 3	23	0.77				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				
Lack of organizational tension	Group 1	<= 3	3	0.10	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a	Effective listening	Group 1	<= 3	5	0.17	0.50	0.000	.000 ^a
	Group 2	> 3	27	0.90			Group 2		> 3	25	0.83				
	Total		30	1.00			Total			30	1.00				

A. Exact Results Are Provided Instead Of Monte Carlo For This Test.

According to the results of Table No. 6, factors (intuition, empathy, talent, industry growth, conscientiousness, social media, leadership style, customer trust, and organizational trust) have not been approved by experts. This means that these seven factors will not affect the sales performance of companies in business-to-business sales.

According to the results of Table No. 6, factors (intuition, empathy, talent, industry growth, conscientiousness, social media, leadership style, customer trust, and organizational trust) have not been approved by experts. This means that these seven factors will not affect the sales performance of companies in intercompany sales.

Conclusion

A better understanding of the factors affecting business-to-business sales performance is important for organizations' optimal performance. A systematic review of the literature related to sales performance at the business-to-business level and the results of interviews with experts in this field showed that four main factors will affect the performance of business-to-business sales. These main factors include individual, organizational, environmental, and customer-level indicators, each with different sub-factors. The results indicate that contrary to the findings of researchers such as Churchill et al. (1985), among individual factors, only talent does not play a role in the success of Business to business sales. Despite the fact that many researchers, such as Itani et al. (2022), Terho et al. (2022), and Bowen et al. (2021), stated that social media affects the success of sales performance; However, in the organizational index of this research, the opposite result was obtained, and we asked the reason for this lack of influence by referring to three experts. They believed that according to how the sales mechanism works at the business-to-business level, social media has no effect or its effect is very small. Organizational trust (related to the organizational index), which in the findings of Jaramillo et al.'s (2006) research, played an important role in sales performance, could not achieve an acceptable level of significance in this research. In addition, contrary to the data of Valteksky's research conducted in 2015, it was shown that sellers can influence buyer behavior by directly reducing the intangibility of the sales offer or by indirectly increasing the buyer's trust in the seller (related to the index at the customer level). In order to improve the company's sales, it was not accepted by the experts in this research. The leadership style related to the organizational index that was considered in the research of Kraus et al. (2015) could not attract the opinion of experts in the current research. In addition to these factors, conscientiousness, which is a part of the individual index, has not been a factor affecting business-to-business sales performance, which Yang et al. confirmed in 2011. Baldauf and Cravens (2002) listed individual abilities (individual index component), industry growth, planning for sales, sales timing, and product type related to organizational index as effective in better sales performance. However, the results of the present study showed that the industry growth factor and sales planning, which are related to the environmental and individual indicators, respectively, will not have an effect on the success of business-to-business sales performance. Finally, contrary to the findings of Anaza et al. (2018) and Mariadoss et al. (2014), empathy and intuition related to individual indicators will not be effective in the success of business-to-business sales performance. Based on these findings, a framework of factors affecting business-to-business (B2B) sales performance has been presented, which is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The model extracted from the research

Suggestion and limitation

It is obvious that this framework of indicators (individual, organizational, environmental, and customer level) needs more testing to achieve validity and reliability in different areas and regions. Although in this research, as in secondary research, the researchers have conducted a comprehensive search of related databases, it cannot be completely sure that all the research related to the performance of inter-company sales has been investigated.

On the other hand, based on the systematic review steps, the quantity of relationships between the factors in the model has not been presented. For this purpose, the need for meta-analysis is felt to investigate the importance and extent of relationships between factors by examining all quantitative studies and to complete the model resulting from this research. Another limitation is that in this research, due to attention to the quality of the articles, in the search for the articles, it emphasized the journal articles that have at least the Scopus and Web of Science profiles. Therefore, other published sources such as conference and conference articles, book chapters, and other magazine articles have not been taken into consideration, and future research needs to examine these sources and compare their results with the current research. In addition, the studies carried out in the performance of intercompany sales are considered, and there is a need to examine the research related to B2C sellers and compare the results with the results of this research. Next, researchers can examine the consequences of the effects of these factors on intercompany sales performance. They can examine how these factors relate to each other. In addition to this, specific areas, such as the service area, etc., should consider the effect of these factors and their results for future research. Finally, managers are suggested to specify these factors according to their company and design and implement the necessary policies accordingly. Also, they can determine the strategies to strengthen each of these factors so that they can successfully improve the final performance of the company and become the market leader in the competitive and turbulent environment of the business world. They should pay attention to doing the best and most important work at the best time and focus on potential customers. Sales forces should be able to compare their results with the bestsellers to identify their performance gaps. By setting goals, defining what they want and how to achieve them, and sharing this information with the manager and other members, sales staff can be on the right track for success in sales performance. The company should also respond to the creative ideas and successful performance of employees in sales with its support through the reward system. In addition, it should help the employees with the necessary training in this field and specify the ethical boundaries. It is important that they remember that in identifying and measuring the factors related to the success of sales performance, they not only focus on official factors and evaluations but also use informal evaluations and interactions so that identifying factors is closer to reality and facilitates the company's success.

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